

Critical Analysis Thakazhi Sivasankankara Pillai's Chemmeen

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Abstract

The paper critically analyses Thakazhi Sivasankara Pillai's Chemmeen. It mainly deals with the struggle and the tragedy of the poor fisher woman Karuthamma and the tradition of fishermen community in Kerala. The central theme of the novel Chemmeen is myth making. The myth is about chastity. The fisherman passed the myth of chastity from generation to generation with strong belief. Then it also talks about the love affair of the protagonist Karuthamma. Chemmeen is not only a story of tragic young love but raises issues of individual morality and action, economic condition and social belief. Chemmeen is a realistic fictional tragedy which focuses on the life style of fishermen folk in Kerala, the south part of India. The incidents of the novel are as realistic as it happens in the real life of poor fishermen in India.

Keywords: Customs and Tradition, Myth-making, Morality, Chastity, Transgressor of Tradition, Realism.

Thakazhi Sivasankara Pillai is one of the famous novelists in Malayalam. He was born in April 17, 1912 and died in April 10, 1999. He received Padma Bhushan award in 1984 and he won the Jnanpith award for the epic novel Kayar (1978). He wrote 39 novels and more than six hundred short stories. He also wrote four autobiographies: Ente Balykala Katha (My Childhood Story, 1967), Ormayude Theerangalil (On the Shores of Memory, 1985), Oru Kuttanadam Katha (A Story of Kuttanad, 1992) and Jeevathinte Oru Edy (A page of life, 1993). Chemmeen is a master piece of Thakazhi Sivasankara Pillai. It was first published in Malayalam in 1956. In 1962, Chemmeen was translated into English by Anita Nair. The translation work of Chemmeen is simple to read. His writings focus on the oppressed class of the society.

Thakazhi Sivasankara Pillai's Chemmeen has mainly reconstructed the myth. The myth is about fisher women's chastity. If the married fisher woman was infidel when her husband was in the sea, the Sea Goddess would consume him. This is the myth, strongly believed in Kerala fishermen community. The wild description of sea shore makes the readers discuss under the topic of ecology. Chemmeen is T.S.Pillai's best novel which expresses the struggle in the lives of the fisherman in Kerala. In this novel Pillai gives many traditional beliefs and customs. The fishermen tradition is broken by Chembankunju and Karuthamma.

Chembankunju is portrayed as the transgressor of tradition and customs. Chembankunju's buying a boat and nets is an offence against customs of fisherman community. Only the Valakkaran is allowed to own boats and net. Valakkaran is a high caste in fishermen community in Kerala. Chembankunju does not follow the age old rules. He gets new boat and nets.

The children of the sea are five kinds: Arayan, valakkaran, mukkavan, marakkan and fifth caste of no particular name... only valakkaran is allowed to own boats and nets. In fact, in the east the protector of the shore, the shore master, would permit only the valakkaran to buy the boat and nets. (31)

From this act of Chembankunju readers can understand he is a transgressor and he is brave enough to break the law of fishermen community. By owning boats and nets Chembankunju is a new trend setter to next generation.

Throughout the novel Chembankunju is described as a greedy man and a villain in some aspects in the novel. Greedy is one of the seven deadly sins which are the ways of going to hell. Chembankunju marries Pappikunju after the death of his wife Chakki. His first daughter, Karuthamma got married. Even after the marriage of his daughter, Chembankunju secondly marries Pappikunju, a young widow. His second daughter Panchami is a young girl leaves her father because of the new arrival of her step mother. After Panchami lives in Karuthamma's house but Chembankunju does not bother about it. This shows Chembankunju does not affection towards his daughters. Chembankunju's only goal in life is to own a boat and a net. He is a strong minded person finally he owns boat and nets with the help of Pareekutty, a young Muslim trader. Who helps Chembankunju with one condition that the fish tug by the bold will be sold to Parrekutty. Chembankunju does not follow condition. So Pareekutty has to face economic problems only because of him.

When you have a boats and nets, will you sell us the fish? If you give us a good price. We will Kalikunju and Nallpennu were grumbling. They had to buy fish from shack owners.... He had a great deal of money in his hands. Life had a whole new radiance. He was treading new path. (59)

Chembankunju's mind is changed after earn lot of money it shows his greedy nature. How people are running behind money, in this path they lost their morality. Chembankunju is a hard worker, he always work twice as much as others. But his lack of morality and cheated Pareekutty make the readers to bad impression on him. Chembankunju is represented poor fisherman economic condition and his only thoughts Chembankunju is reveals important of money making in the world.

Karuthamma's marriage decision is taken by Chembankunju. He does not ask any opinion from his daughter. It shows old tradition and male domination. When he sees Palani in sea expeditions suddenly he makes a decision to arrange marriage between Palani and Karuthamma for his own profit. Chembankunju is not at all a good father and good person. He is a typical money minded person in poor fishermen community. Chembankunju embraced Palani with the intention of amassing a lot of money: "He said "you are the sea's prince; my boy? Palani didn't speak. That day it was Palani's catch which fetched the best price. And so Chembankunju suffered a small loss" (81)

Chembankunju's attitude shows that at any way he wants to attain high position in his community. We come cross such a characters in our life. It shows T.S.Pillai's characterizations are realistic and it has depicted accurately the fisherman community and their economic problems. Through the character of Chembankunju the novelist has excellently portrayed the economic condition of fishermen community.

This novel also focuses on the religious attitude of fisherwomen. The fishermen community worships the Sea Goddess (Kadalamma, literally means Mother Sea). In early part of the novel Karuthamma work ships the Sea Goddess has blessed us. The mythological facts also depend

on the Sea Goddess. If the married woman has an affair when her husband is in the sea. The Sea Goddess will destroy her husband people have deep faith in Sea Goddess because they work in the sea. They get all things from sea and everything in their life is given by sea God. The Sea Goddess also gives protection to them.

Chakki, mother of Karuthamma completely follows old tradition. She is a fisher woman born and brought up on the seaside. And an inheritor of a tradition of sea shore. In this novel Chakki continuously tells to Karuthamma about virtue of fisherwomen Chakki says:

How did he escape the tempest? Why wasn't he swallowed by the whale... only because a chaste wife had stood on the seaside, praying and waiting for her husband's safe return... 'Do you know why the sea cries at times? The sea knows that if the sea mother gets angry, all will be ruined. But if she is pleased she will give you everything my child. There is gold on the sea, my daughter, gold! Virtue is the most important thing, my daughter. Purity of the body and mind! "A fisherman's wealth is his fisher woman's virtue. (8-9)

From this conversation between Chakki and her daughter T.S.Pillai adds strength to myth and virtue of fisher women. In this novel there is no word about men's chastity. Only women have to be virtuous. Men need not be virtuous. From the ancient time onwards only the female have purity and virtues. No, one talks about male's chastity.

Chemmeen is also a novel about forbidden love and barriers of fisherman. Karuthamma loves Pareekutty a young Muslim. But she marries Palani, an orphan, young talented man. Karuthamma lives with Palani happily. When she hears the cry of Pareekutty there is a turning point of her life. Palani's wife Karuthamma goes to see Pareekutty at one night while her husband in the sea. Their old love is awakened. Palani is bitten by a whale and he is swallowed by the sea. The dead bodies of Pareekutty and Karuthamma locked in an embraced are found on sea shore. This is the end of the forbidden love story.

In this novel Chemmeen fishermen community people gossip about Karuthamma and Pareekutty. It really wounded Palani. Every time there had been rumors about shack owners who seduced women. "No one really knew the gravitas of that relationship could a Muslim shack owner be in love with a fisher girl? No one said love couldn't happen. But it had never happened before that's the fact (215)". "The gossip about Karuthamma trickled into his ears. What a disaster! A fallen woman's husband going to see in his boat. (175)"

In Indian society people always gossip and are hypocrites about women. Likewise here people create some rumors about Karuthamma and Pareekutty. Hypocrisy is well flourished in rural and folk villages.

Chemmeen also shows oppression of women both physically and sentimentally. Here Karuthamma suffers from women's suppression. She is emotionally blackmailed by her mother Chakki. For the sake of her mother and father Karuthamma rejects Pareekutty and sacrifices her love. Chembankunju and Chakki do not accept love affair of Karuthamma and Pareekutty because Pareekutty is a Muslim boy. If they get married it is an inter-caste, inter-religious marriage the so called society does not accept them.

Now day's honour killing is a serious issue in Tamil Nadu. The government of Tamil Nadu takes step to avoid honour killing. In spite of that numerous young couples are killed in this case. Society is a reason for the separation of Karuthamma and Pareekutty. Only for the sake of the society that parents do not accept their love. Chemmeen is a reflection of social evils.

The novel Chemmeen is a tragedy. It creates a sense of pity and fear in the mind of the audience or readers. The novel ends sadly and it creates pity for Karuthamma and Pareekutty and sorrow for Palani. Just like Indian epics this novel revolves around the main theme of the chastity of women, which is the main aspect in the myth of fishermen community.

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